

NOTES

Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) Carboxylate Complexes with Nitrogen Ligands

R. N. RAY

Department of Chemistry, Angul Science College, Angul
and

B. K. MOHAPATRA

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-3
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COMPLEXES of metal carboxylates, particularly the acetato complexes, are interesting because acetato group can be monodentate, bidentate (chelating or bridging) giving rise to different coordination numbers and stereochemistries when the transition metal acetates are complexed with heterocyclic amines. A lot of work has been done on halogeno-substituted acetates^{1,2} to study the variation in the coordinating ability of acetato group by halogen substitution. Though Lever and Ogden³ have studied the complexes of acetates, mono- and dichloro acetates of transition metal ions, trichloro acetato complexes have not been investigated. We have been studying the complexation of some divalent metal ion carboxylates⁴ with nitrogen ligands and reported earlier complexes of trichloro acetates⁵ and phenyl acetates⁶. It was thought worthwhile to extend the investigation to some metal dicarboxylates and this communication reports complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) succinate and phthalates with amines.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Succinates and phthalates of different metals were dissolved in absolute ethanol, treated with nitrogen ligands in 1 : 4 proportion and the solution refluxed

for thirty minutes over water bath. On cooling overnight compounds separated out. These were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Metal in complexes was estimated by EDTA titration method and nitrogen by standard micro-analytical method. Conductance was measured in $M/1000$ acetone solution of the complexes using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens by Gouy method using $[\text{HgCo}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrant. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr phase using a Beckman-I.R. 12 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on Hilgerwatt uvispek spectrophotometer with $M/100$ (chloroform-amine) solution of the complexes. All the relevant analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the zinc and copper(II) complexes reported here, have the composition $M(\text{L or L}')(\text{Am})_2$; nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes are of the formula $M(\text{L or L}')(\text{Am})_4$, except the blue crystalline complex which is of the composition $\text{CoL}'(\text{Am})_2$.

The carboxylates give rise⁷ to a strong asymmetrical stretching band near $1650\text{--}1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and weaker symmetrical band near 1400 cm^{-1} . In the metal carboxylates studied these two bands appear ~ 1580 and $\sim 1380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ by shifting to lower frequency regions, compared to the sodium salts. In the complexes with nitrogen ligands these bands again shift to higher frequency region and are observed $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, thus providing direct evidence of bonding by the carboxylate anion and the nitrogen ligands. Further, most of the absorption bands due to free amines are modified on bonding to the metal ions. This has

TABLE-1 ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF CARBOXYLATE COMPLEXES

Compounds	Colour & form	M.P.	Conductance (mhos. cm^2)	μ eff B.M.	% Metal		% Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd
CoL B ₄	Pink cryst	120	10.8	5.1	12.35	12.63	11.71	11.99
CoL Q ₄	—do—	235	8.2	4.9	8.15	8.51	7.85	8.11
CoL' B ₄	Black Amp.	250	8.5	5.2	11.05	11.38	10.58	10.81
CoL' Q ₄	Deep blue cryst	238	10.5	4.6	12.01	12.23	5.56	5.82
NiL Q ₄	Green cryst	178	6.8	2.9	8.31	8.5	7.89	8.11
NiL' Q ₄	—do—	185	9.4	3.1	7.68	7.94	7.32	7.58
CuL B ₂	Blue cryst	190	10.4	1.78	19.32	19.52	8.24	8.6
CuL' Q ₂	Green cryst	210	10.5	1.75	14.26	14.52	6.02	6.4
CuL' B ₂	Violet cryst	138	8.6	1.81	16.85	17.1	7.15	7.50
CuL' Q ₂	Blue cryst	235	9.8	1.83	12.85	13.09	5.35	5.77
ZnL B ₂	White cryst	240	6.9		19.78	19.97	8.94	8.55
ZnL Q ₂	—do—	218	6.8		14.65	14.88	6.12	6.37
ZnL' B ₂	—do—	250	8.5		17.01	17.42	7.15	7.46
ZnL' Q ₂	—do—	189	8.4		19.05	18.42	5.48	5.75

Q=quinoline, B=Diethylamine, L'=anion of phthalic acid, L=Anion of succinic acid.

been further substantiated by observation of bands ~ 380 and ~ 450 cm^{-1} in the far-infrared region, attributable⁸ to ν (M-N) and ν (M-O) respectively.

In the electronic spectra, Co(II) complexes give rise to two absorption bands $\sim 18-19$ and ~ 8.6 K.K. regions attributable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(P)$ transition respectively. Position of absorption bands, the extinction coefficient values and magnetic moment suggests an octahedral or distorted octahedral configuration for these complexes. The deep blue cobalt complex shows one intense band at 16.0(980) K.K. due to ${}^4A_g \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition. The other bands are outside the range of spectrophotometer used. Molar absorptivity value and magnetic moment of this complex confirms a tetrahedral geometry.

Three absorption bands appear in case of Nickel(II) complexes in the 8.7-9, 14-15.5 and 25.6 K. K. regions assignable⁹ to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. An octahedral or distorted octahedral structure is suggested for these complexes.

Cu(II) complexes show one broad absorption band ~ 15.0 K.K. region. Though a number of transitions are expected for the copper(II) complex, they are very close in energy and often give rise to one broad band envelope. Hence these complexes are presumably have a planar coordination.

On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral studies, zinc complexes may have a tetrahedral environment around the metal ion.

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Titrimetric Determination of 2, 4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenyl Chloride with Sodium Methoxide in Non-aqueous Media

(Miss), NEELAM KHANNA and K.S. BOPARAI
School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University,
Ujjain-456 010

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THE unique properties of 2, 4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride¹ has made it extremely valuable to researchers in various fields, and oftentimes one is required to carry out its determination. An iodometric method² for its determination is known. The determination of solutions of 2, 4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride in benzene methanol, nitrobenzene, ethylene chloride, carbon tetrachloride, and dimethyl formamide with sodium methoxide as titrant and thymol blue as indicator, has been studied and is described here. The results are reliable (Table 1) except for dimethylformamide in which case the end point was unreliable.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF 2, 4-DINITROBENZENE-SULPHENYL CHLORIDE (DSC)* WITH SODIUM METHOXIDE

Solvent	DSC, taken mg	DSC, found mg	% Deviation
Benzene-Methanol	10.49	10.47	-0.19
"	21.46	21.50	+0.18
"	22.26	22.23	-0.13
"	32.40	32.47	+0.21
"	51.40	51.52	+0.22
"	52.28	52.18	-0.18
"	71.02	71.02	0.00
"	92.91	100.11	+8.20
"	140.02	139.82	-0.14
"	179.08	179.27	+0.13
Ethylene chloride	10.00	9.98	-0.20
"	25.01	25.01	0.00
"	50.03	50.04	+0.19
"	90.07	90.01	-0.06
Carbon tetrachloride	14.80	14.78	-0.13
"	24.03	24.05	+0.08
"	27.21	27.21	0.00
"	48.80	48.88	+0.06
"	50.82	50.87	+0.09
Nitrobenzene	13.09	13.09	0.00
"	24.60	24.67	+0.28
"	50.01	50.02	+0.02
"	79.03	79.09	+0.07

* Purity of DSC was checked by the iodometric procedure².

Procedure :

The solution of sodium methoxide (0.02 N for samples less than 50 mg and 0.04 N for the remaining samples) is prepared in benzene-methanol³ and standardized against benzoic acid. 2, 4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride⁴ is dissolved in a minimum amount of a-solvent in a conical flask. Twenty-five ml of benzene-methanol (3 : 1) and two drops of thymol blue (0.3% W/V, in methanol) are introduced. The solution is titrated with sodium